

The Relationship between the usage of Drugs and Sport Performance

Vincent Parnabas¹, Julinamary Parnabas², Antoinette Mary Parnabas³

¹Faculty of Sport Science and Recreation, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia

²Institut Pendidikan Guru Kampus Darulaman Jitra, Kedah, Malaysia

³Medical Unit, Hospital Taiping, Taiping, Perak, Malaysia

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Research also suggest that substance used is not caused by defective socialization or lack of moral values among athletes, in fact it often occurs among the most dedicated, committed and hard working athletes in sports (3). The German sport literature during 1920's and 1930's offered antidoping sermons, justifications for the use of various substances and rationales for drawing lines between what should and should not be forbidden (8). A good sport psychologist equips athletes with skills to perform well in sport competitions without using drugs. A significant task for the sport psychologist and coaches is to discover ways to improve athletes self confidence, in order to stop athletes from using drugs to enhance self confidence and their performance.

Competition is an important part of athletes' life. Competitions in sports frequently have been defended in terms of the search for excellence in performance. For those athletes who cope well, competitions allow them to develop and enhance their abilities. However, a good number of athletes are sore-losers. They have taken steroids and other drugs to enhance their performance. The bad effects of these drugs will only manifest later, but yet these athletes are willing to take such risks just to win.

For centuries athletes have taken a wide variety of substances to aid their performance. However, when

ABSTRACT

The main challenges for sports psychologist and coaches in this century would be producing strong performance among the nondrug addict athletes. Relatively widespread use of such drugs as namely anabolic steroids to enhance performance dates back at least to the Olympic of the 1960's, although broad public awareness of such drugs use seems relatively recent. The easy availability of drugs, through illegal, contributes to the rise of drug addictions. This research explores some rationales of regulating drug use by athletes in order to determine the level of sport performance. The sample consisted of 97 athletes, drawn from athletes who competed in sports between Universities. Drug Usage Questionnaire and Sport Performance were used to collect the data. The correlation coefficient of 0.712 was noted respectively between the usage of drugs and sports performance. Even though the usage of drugs benefits the sports performance, but it is considered as cheating and unfair, harm, perversion of sports, unnaturalness and dehumanization. The government, sport psychology, counselors, coaches and sports bodies should play an important role to face the challenges to overcome the evil, drug-enhances to protect athletes' health and to achieve fair level playing field.

KEYWORDS: Drugs, enhance performance, sports performance

BACKGROUND

One of the main challenges for sport psychologist and coaches in this century would be producing strong performance among the non drug addict athletes. Drug, as a new 'threat' to the ideal of sports has entered into the sport scene lately.

athletes attempt to achieve excellence through the use of performance-enhancing drugs, there is widespread condemnation. Condemnation of doping on ethical grounds appeared during the 1920's as sports became a genuine mass-cultural phenomenon (8). However, the usage of drugs among athletes is unknown. Although the prevalence of drugs use among professional, elite amateur and collegiate athletes is unknown, a report of Victor Conte, drugs supplier for athletes, told "The Times" that six out of 10 athletes at the games are taking banned substances (18). The relatively widespread use of such drugs as anabolic steroids to enhance performance dates back at least to the Olympic of the 1960's, although broad public awareness of such drugs use seems relatively recent (13).

(9) distinguished three kinds of drugs, such as recreational drugs, restorative drugs and additive drugs. Recreational drugs are drugs such as alcohol, cocaine, heroin, marijuana and a host of other street drugs. Typically, recreational drugs are taken without medical supervision and many are illegal. Restorative drugs, by contrast, are drugs such as aspirin and antihypertensive medications. These typical permit people suffering from a medical disorder to approximate their normal functioning. Addictive drugs, such as anabolic steroids, boost athletes' level of performance.

Athletes claimed that the anabolic-androgenic steroids produced a significant increase in their muscle strength, blood volume, red blood cells and muscle size that supported the enhancement of athletic performance (14; 17). Athletes also use depressants, such as barbiturates, sedative-hypnotics and alcohol to relieve tension, depression and anxiety to enhance performance (6).

Many athletes in Malaysia and other countries are victims of drug addictions. For example, in 2013, former athletics sports was punished with a six-year ban after being found guilty for his involvement in two separate doping scandals. In 2012, a Malaysia Games silver medalist failed a drug test after his silver-medal effort at the Sukma game traces of an unidentified banned substance were found in his urine sample. In 2002, Sepak takraw trio champions were sent home from the Asian Games in Busan after failing a random dope test (15). The easily availability of drugs illegally, contributes to the rise of drug addictions. The use of tranquilizers, pain controllers, mood controllers, chemical stimulants, antidepressants, fat burners, vitamins, creatine, insulin, caffeine, nicotine, muscle builders, prohormones and hormones, among dozens of other pervasive substances (4). Drug companies market their products as necessary for social means such as sexual performance enhancement, intellectuality, work performance, health maintenance, strength building, counteracting negative effects of aging (4; 8). Furthermore, the list of widely used substances grows longer as new discoveries are made and new supplements are produced and sold. For example, scientists have already been able to manipulate the genes of cows to inhibit the myostatin gene, which is responsible for inhibiting muscle growth. The result is that the cows produce twice as much muscle as a normal cow. It is only a matter of time before this technology is used in human trials (16). Therefore, sport psychologist and coaches, faced a very a strong challenge in this century to stop athletes from taking drugs in enhancing their performance.

AIM OF THE STUDY

This research explores some rationales of regulating drug use by athletes in order to determine the level of sports performance. The aim of this research was to correlate the relationship between the level of drug usage and sport performance.

METHODOLOGY

The sample consisted of 97 athletes, who voluntary participated in this study. The sample was drawn from athletes who competed in Majlis Sukan Universiti Malaysia (MASUM) or Sports between Universities. Drugs Usage Questionnaire was used which comprised for winning (5 items), reduce the level of anxiety and stress (5 items), reduce the feeling of pain (5 items) and the influence of athletes (5 items). Besides that, the Questionnaire of Sports Performance (10 items) were used in this research to collect the data.

RESULT

Level of drugs usage and Sports Performance

The correlation coefficient of 0.712 was noted between the usage of drugs and sports performance in the evaluation of 97 athletes, which is significantly ($P < .01$). In other words, the positive relationship existing between these variables is statistically significant (Table 2).

Table 2: The Relationship between the Usage of Drugs and Sports Performance among Athletes

Subject	Sport Performance
The Usage of Drugs	0.712** (0.000)

** $p < .01$

DISCUSSION

Level of drugs usage and Sports Performance

The result showed the existence of positive correlation between the usage of drugs and sport performance. In other words, the higher the usage of drugs, the higher the level of sport performance. The findings gained in the present research supported the research done by (5), (10) and (3), that taking drugs can increase sports performance.

Even though, the present research revealed that the usage of drugs has enhance the performance of athletes, but taking risk in sports, is inevitably irrational, self-destructive and immature. Taking substances is improper as a means to winning in sports. Sports suppose to promote health and fitness but taking drugs to enhance performance on the long run can cause hazards to health and even death.

When an athlete at the highest level, they live with a huge pressure from the fans, parents, coach, university, sponsors and so on. Hence, ambitious to perform at the excellent level is the driving force behind the use of drugs on most athletes.

Furthermore, drugs make it possible to achieve better performance without additional training, which is considered as unethical (2).

CONCLUSION

Even though the present research showed that taking drugs benefits the athletes in terms of increasing the sports performance, but it is a cheating, foul play, unfair, dishonest and unsportsmanlike actions. Furthermore, damaging effects on growth patterns and on psychosocial development, even risk of death or permanent injury, are probable high risks of taking drugs among athletes. The most difficult question is how the sport psychologist and coaches going to face the challenges to curb this illegal activities? The government, sport psychology, counselors, coaches and sports bodies should play an important role to face the challenges to overcome the evil, drug-enhances, among athletes. Drug testing is needed to protect athletes' health and to achieve fair level field playing. Mental skills training is the most obvious and valuable, which sport psychologist can provide in order to prevent athletes from using drugs to enhance self confidence and performance. Sport psychologist should play an important role to teach athletes' skills and strategies relating to motivation, anxiety and stress management, concentration, self confidence and mental practice. Athletes should learn mental skills to enhance self confidence and sports performance from sport psychologists to combat the use of drugs.

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